

The Morbid Impact of Environmental Toxins on the Human Nervous System: Central Sleep Apnea Nexus with Organic Solvents, Pesticides, and Heavy Metals

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Abstract

This review explores how organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals, as prevalent environmental toxins, impact human health, particularly the nervous system, and their association with central sleep apnea (CSA). These toxins disrupt neural function through various mechanisms, including direct neurotoxic effects, neurotransmission interference, oxidative stress induction, and inflammatory responses. Organic solvents, prevalent in industrial and household products, compromise neuronal membrane integrity, disrupt neurotransmitter balance, and induce oxidative stress. These effects impair neuronal signaling critical for regulating breathing during sleep, contributing to CSA development. Pesticides inhibit enzymes involved in neurotransmitter production and disrupt neurotransmitter receptor function, leading to imbalances that affect respiratory control. Oxidative stress induced by pesticides further exacerbates neuronal damage, impairing the brainstem's ability to maintain regular breathing patterns. Heavy metals interfere with neuronal ion channels, induce oxidative stress, and trigger inflammatory responses in the nervous system. These disruptions impair neuronal function in the brainstem responsible for respiratory regulation, resulting in apnea episodes during sleep. The diagnosis of toxin-induced CSA involves comprehensive evaluations, including exposure history, physical examinations, neuroimaging, laboratory tests, polysomnography, and neurophysiological testing. Differential diagnosis excludes other potential causes, ensuring accurate identification of toxin-induced CSA. Treatment strategies focus on eliminating toxin exposure, pharmacological interventions to manage symptoms, adjunctive therapies, and nutritional support. Managing toxin-induced CSA requires a multidisciplinary approach involving pulmonologists, neurologists, and toxicologists, among others, to optimize patient outcomes through targeted interventions and ongoing monitoring. Education and counseling promote patient engagement by fostering a comprehensive understanding and effective management of the condition—enhancing overall respiratory health and patient quality of life (QoL).

Keywords: *Congenital Central Hypoventilation Syndrome, Demyelination, Impair Nerve Signal Transmission, PAP Devices, Proinflammatory Cytokines, Vitamin Deficiencies.*

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Introduction

History of Central Sleep Apnea (CSA)

CSA, a disorder marked by intermittent cessation of breathing during sleep due to the disruption in the brain's ability to transmit neuronal signals to the respiratory muscles, has garnered increased attention in

the medical literature (Eckert, Jordan, Merchia, & Malhotra, 2007). Unlike obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), CSA is linked explicitly to central nervous system (CNS) dysfunction.

Historical documentation of sleep-related breathing disorders can be found in ancient medical texts from various cultures. However, the specific recognition of CSA as a distinct entity has been more recent (Memon & Manganaro, 2023).

Advancements in Understanding CSA

Substantial progress has been made in understanding the causal factors of CSA (Rana & Sankari, 2023). Exposure to environmental toxins has been shown to disrupt the neural pathways responsible for regulating breathing during sleep (J. Liu, Ghastine, Um, Rovit, & Wu, 2021). Organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals are particularly concerning due to their potential to cause oxidative stress, inflammatory responses, and neuronal damage, which can interfere with the brain's respiratory centers and contribute to the development or exacerbation of CSA (Ijomone et al., 2020).

Epidemiology and Prevalence

CSA is a relatively prevalent condition, particularly among older adults and those with underlying health conditions (e.g., heart failure and stroke). Prevalence estimates for CSA vary widely depending on the population studied and the diagnostic criteria used (Rana & Sankari, 2023). It is generally estimated that CSA affects approximately 0.9% of the adult population, with higher rates observed in specific groups, e.g., patients with chronic heart failure (Cheyne-Stokes respiration) and those exposed to significant levels of environmental toxins (Rudrappa, Modi, & Bollu, 2023).

Chronic CSA, defined as symptoms persisting for more than six months, can severely impact the quality of life (QoL; Megari, 2013). The condition often goes undiagnosed due to its subtle symptoms compared to OSA, and the prevalence rates may be underreported due to varying symptom perceptions and individual reporting behaviors (Slowik, Sankari, & Collen, 2024).

Impact of CSA on Individuals

CSA can profoundly affect individuals, significantly impairing their QoL and overall well-being (Rana & Sankari, 2023). The recurrent breathing interruptions can lead to severe sleep disturbances, daytime fatigue, cognitive impairment, and an increased risk of cardiovascular events. These adverse health effects can exacerbate psychosocial stress in individuals, leading to anxiety, depression, and a diminished capacity to perform daily activities (Institute of Medicine, 2006a).

CSA has significant implications for various aspects of women's health, including pregnancy and fertility. CSA can have detrimental effects on physiological and hormonal balance, which are vital for reproductive health (Annexure 1).

Impact of CSA on Society

From a societal perspective, CSA imposes considerable economic burdens due to healthcare costs associated with diagnostic evaluations, treatments, and ongoing management of the condition. Indirect costs include productivity losses due to decreased work efficiency, absenteeism, and disability claims (Borsoi, Armeni, Donin, Costa, & Ferini-Strambi, 2022).

The overall economic impact underscores the importance of applying effective diagnostic protocols and management strategies to alleviate symptoms and improve outcomes for individuals affected by CSA.

Discussion

Central sleep apnea (CSA) is classified primarily as a respiratory disorder characterized by interruptions in breathing during sleep. However, it prominently involves neurological components stemming from impaired signaling within the brain responsible for regulating respiratory muscle activity. Thus, CSA is recognized as a condition associated with both the respiratory and nervous systems.

Specific Environmental Toxins: Impact on Human Nervous System and CSA

Organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals—prevalent environmental toxins—harm various human body systems and contribute to a broad range of medical conditions, including CSA. These toxins can disrupt neural function through direct neurotoxic effects, interference with neurotransmission, and induction of oxidative stress and inflammatory responses.

Organic Solvents

Organic solvents are widely used in industrial settings and household products, including paints, adhesives, and cleaning agents (Dick, 2006). Exposure to these solvents can occur through inhalation, ingestion, or dermal contact. Once in the body, organic solvents can damage the nervous system by disrupting neuronal membrane integrity, neurotransmitter release, and synaptic transmission (National Research Council, 1990).

Cellular level disruption:

Organic solvents alter the lipid bilayers of neuronal membranes, affecting membrane fluidity and permeability. The lipid bilayer maintains neuronal membranes' structural integrity and function. When organic solvents disrupt this layer, they compromise the membrane's fluidity and permeability, essential for the proper functioning of neurons. This disruption can impair cellular signaling, as the affected neurons lose their ability to transmit electrical impulses effectively (Alberts et al., 2002). This impairment is critical in CSA, where the brain's ability to regulate breathing is disrupted.

Neurotransmitter imbalance:

Organic solvents interfere with vital neuronal processes, e.g., neurotransmitter release, synaptic transmission, and ion channel function (Sheffler, Reddy, & Pillarisetty, 2023). Neurotransmitters, e.g., gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) and glutamate, are essential in maintaining neuronal excitability and inhibition. Organic solvents can cause imbalances in these neurotransmitters. A decrease in GABA can result in excessive neuronal firing, while an imbalance in glutamate can lead to excitotoxicity (de Leon & Tadi, 2023). Both effects disrupt the normal balance of neuronal activity, which is necessary for maintaining regular breathing patterns during sleep. In CSA, this imbalance can disrupt the brain's ability to send signals to respiratory muscles.

Oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction:

Oxidative stress induced by organic solvents further exacerbates neuronal damage. These solvents stimulate the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and impair the body's antioxidant defense mechanisms. The resulting oxidative damage affects proteins, lipids, and DNA, leading to widespread cellular dysfunction (Juan, de la Lastra, Plou, & Pérez-Lebeña, 2021). Mitochondria are particularly vulnerable to oxidative stress. When mitochondrial function is compromised, cells cannot produce enough energy, leading to neuronal injury and dysfunction. In CSA, mitochondrial dysfunction in the neurons of the brainstem can impair their ability to maintain normal respiratory rhythms during sleep (Q. Liu et al., 2022).

CSA development:

The combined effects of membrane disruption, neurotransmitter imbalance, and oxidative stress create a hostile environment for neuronal function. In the brainstem, which regulates involuntary breathing, these disruptions can lead to a failure in the automatic control of breathing. This failure results in periods where breathing stops during sleep. The brain's inability to maintain regular respiratory signals due to the cumulative damage from organic solvents is a key factor in CSA development.

Pesticides

Pesticides, commonly employed in agriculture, penetrate the body via inhalation, ingestion, or dermal contact. Exposure can cause neurotoxicity through mechanisms that impair nerve signal transmission. These chemicals can disrupt neurotransmitter synthesis and release, as well as receptor activation, encouraging imbalances in neural communication and CSA development (Wen et al., 2023).

Inhibition of enzymes and neurotransmitter imbalances:

At the cellular level, pesticides inhibit enzymes involved in neurotransmitter production. For example, acetylcholinesterase inhibitors, a class of pesticides, prevent the breakdown of acetylcholine in the synaptic cleft. This inhibition leads to excessive accumulation of acetylcholine, causing continuous stimulation of neurons, which disrupts normal neurotransmitter levels and signaling (Teleanu et al., 2022). Such imbalances in neurotransmitter levels can disturb the normal functioning of the autonomic nervous system, which regulates involuntary functions, e.g., breathing. In CSA, this can result in the brain's failure to maintain consistent breathing patterns during sleep.

Disruption of neurotransmitter receptor function:

Functionally, pesticides can bind to neurotransmitter receptors on the postsynaptic membrane, either mimicking or blocking the actions of endogenous neurotransmitters. Organophosphate pesticides can bind to acetylcholine receptors, leading to persistent activation or inhibition of neural pathways. This binding disrupts nerve signal propagation, impairing synaptic dysfunction and neuronal communication (Purves et al., 2001). The brainstem relies on precise neurotransmitter signaling to regulate respiratory rhythms. Disruption of this signaling can lead to the onset and persistence of CSA, as the brainstem intermittently fails to send signals to the respiratory muscles.

Oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction:

Oxidative stress is another prominent mechanism by which pesticides disrupt nerve signal transmission (Sule, Condon, & Gomes, 2022). Pesticides provoke the production of ROS and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), which damage cellular components, including proteins, lipids, and DNA. This oxidative damage impairs mitochondrial function, which is crucial for neuron energy production. Neurons are highly dependent on oxidative phosphorylation for their energy needs. With compromised mitochondrial function, neurons cannot sustain their high energy demands, leading to impaired nerve signal transmission (Fricker, Tolkovsky, Borutaite, Coleman, & Brown, 2018). In CSA, oxidative stress-induced neuronal damage in the brainstem can impair its ability to regulate breathing, contributing to episodes of apnea during sleep.

CSA development:

The combined effects of enzyme inhibition, receptor disruption, and oxidative stress create a detrimental environment for neuronal function. In the brainstem, these disruptions can lead to a failure in the automatic control of breathing—resulting in periods where breathing ceases during sleep. The brain's inability to maintain consistent respiratory signals due to the cumulative damage from pesticide exposure is a key factor in CSA development.

Heavy Metals

Heavy metals (e.g., arsenic, cadmium, lead, manganese, and mercury), prevalent in industrial pollutants and e-waste, enter the body via inhalation and ingestion or penetrate via dermal contact. Notably, vulnerable populations such as children and pregnant women face significant lead exposure hazards from lead pipes in drinking water systems (Annexure 2). Exposure can induce neurotoxicity through multiple mechanisms, leading to CSA. These mechanisms include disrupting neuronal ion channels, inducing oxidative stress, and triggering inflammatory responses (P. Chen et al., 2016).

Disruption of ion channels:

At the cellular level, heavy metals interfere with ion channels—specialized proteins in the cell membrane that regulate the flow of ions (e.g., sodium, potassium, calcium, and chloride; Grider, Jessu, & Kabir, 2023). Ion channels are essential for generating and propagating action potentials along nerve fibers. When heavy metals disrupt these channels, they impair the ability of neurons to generate and propagate action potentials effectively. This disruption alters neuronal excitability and impairs signal transmission, which can lead to irregularities in the autonomic regulation of breathing (Grider et al., 2023). In the case of CSA, the impaired signal transmission in the brainstem neurons can lead to the cessation of breath during sleep.

Induction of oxidative stress:

Oxidative stress induced by heavy metals further exacerbates neuronal damage. Heavy metals stimulate the production of ROS and impair the body's antioxidant defense mechanisms. Excessive ROS can cause oxidative damage to cellular components, including proteins, lipids, and DNA (Afzal et al., 2023). This oxidative damage harms neurons because it can disrupt cellular processes and lead to cell death. Additionally, oxidative stress can impair mitochondrial function. Neurons require high amounts of energy to function correctly, and when mitochondrial function is compromised, they cannot meet these energy demands, leading to neuronal dysfunction and injury (Picca et al., 2020). In CSA, oxidative stress-induced damage to brainstem neurons can impair their ability to regulate breathing, contributing to apnea episodes during sleep.

Triggering inflammatory responses:

Heavy metals also trigger inflammatory responses in the nervous system. Exposure to these metals can lead to the release of proinflammatory cytokines and activation of immune cells, e.g., microglia and astrocytes. These inflammatory processes can cause neuronal injury, demyelination, and axonal degeneration. Inflammation in the brainstem can disrupt the neural circuits that regulate breathing, leading to impaired respiratory rhythms and contributing to the development and persistence of CSA (L. Chen et al., 2017).

CSA development:

The cumulative effect of these disruptions—ion channel interference, oxidative stress, and inflammation—can severely compromise the brain's ability to maintain normal respiratory rhythms during sleep. In the brainstem, these combined effects can lead to a failure in the automatic regulation of breathing, resulting in periods of apnea. The brain's intermittent inability to send signals to the respiratory muscles due to the cumulative damage from heavy metal exposure is a key factor in the development of CSA.

Table 1 outlines the underlying mechanisms and impacts of organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals on CSA.

Table 1. Mechanisms and Impacts of CSA-Inducing Organic Solvents, Pesticides, and Heavy Metals

Environmental Toxins	Mechanism	Nervous System's Role	Impact
Organic Solvents	Disruption of neuronal membrane integrity, neurotransmitter release, and synaptic transmission.	Affects central nervous system (CNS), impairing respiratory control centers	Damage to central respiratory pathways, leading to neurotransmitter imbalances and oxidative stress, contributing to CSA
Pesticides	Inhibition of enzymes involved in neurotransmitter production, interference with exocytosis, and receptor activation	Disrupts neural signaling, affecting central respiratory pathways	Disruption of nerve signal transmission in central respiratory pathways, oxidative stress, and neuronal damage, leading to CSA
Heavy Metals	Disruption of ion channels, oxidative stress, and inflammatory responses	Affects neural conductivity and integrity, impairing central respiratory pathways	Aberrant ion flux and impaired action potential propagation in central respiratory pathways, oxidative damage, and neuronal injury, leading to CSA

Table 2 details the specific mechanisms associated with each toxin type and their impact on health issues like CSA.

Table 2. Mechanisms of Toxicity Contributing to CSA by Organic Solvents, Pesticides, and Heavy Metals

Mechanism	Organic Solvents	Pesticides	Heavy Metals
Alter lipid bilayers of neuronal membranes	☒		
Interfere with neurotransmitter release	☒	☒	
Interfere with synaptic transmission	☒		
Interfere with ion channels	☒	☒	☒
Imbalance in neurotransmitters			
Disrupt nerve propagation		☒	
Provoke ROS production	☒	☒	☒
Provoke RNS production		☒	
Disrupt brainstem control of breathing	☒	☒	☒
Induction of inflammatory cytokines		☒	☒
Activation of immune cells in the nervous system		☒	☒

The impact of these environmental toxins on CSA necessitates preventive measures and targeted therapies to mitigate their harmful effects on the human nervous system.

CSA: Assessment Resulting from Environmental Toxin Exposure

Patient History: A detailed exposure history, including occupational or environmental toxin exposure, is crucial. This history should document the duration, intensity, and type of exposure to organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals (Institute of Medicine, 1995).

Physical Examination: The assessment focuses on respiratory symptoms, particularly episodes of interrupted breathing during sleep. Evaluation includes observing signs of neurological impairment that might indicate CNS involvement (Slowik et al., 2024).

Neuroimaging: Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can detect structural abnormalities or signs of toxicity in the brain regions responsible for respiratory control (Ciumas, Rheims, & Ryvlin, 2022). Imaging helps identify potential lesions or damage in the brainstem and other CSA-associated central structures (Yuan, Zuo, & Xu, 2022).

Laboratory Tests:

- **Blood and urine tests:** These tests measure specific toxin levels (e.g., blood lead and urine organic solvent levels). Elevated levels of these toxins can indicate significant exposure contributing to CSA (Wani, Ara, & Usmani, 2016).
- **Biomarkers of neurotoxicity or metabolic disturbances:** Assessing biomarkers can help identify the extent of neurotoxic damage or metabolic imbalances due to toxin exposure (Roberts et al., 2015).

Neurological Examination:

- **Sensory examination:** Assess sensory abnormalities, e.g., numbness or tingling, which might suggest broader neurological impairment (Shahrokhi & Asuncion, 2023).
- **Reflexes:** Test reflexes, including respiratory reflexes, to evaluate neurological function and potential CNS involvement (Shahrokhi & Asuncion, 2023).
- **Balance evaluation:** Observe any abnormalities in balance or coordination that may accompany CSA, indicating more extensive neurological effects (Shahrokhi & Asuncion, 2023).

Polysomnographic Testing: Comprehensive sleep study (polysomnography) to monitor various physiological parameters during sleep, including brain waves, oxygen levels in the blood, heart rate, breathing patterns, and eye and leg movements (Gerstenslager & Slowik, 2023). This test helps differentiate between obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) and CSA by identifying central apneas with a lack of respiratory effort (Akbarian, Ghahjaverestan, Yadollahi, & Taati, 2020).

Neurophysiological Testing: While primarily used for auditory conditions, auditory brainstem response (ABR) testing can be adapted to evaluate the brainstem’s function, which is crucial in regulating breathing. This test provides metrics about the nature and extent of neural involvement in CSA (Young, Cornejo, & Spinner, 2023).

Exclusion of Other Causes: A differential diagnosis is necessary to exclude inherited respiratory disorders, autoimmune conditions affecting the CNS, infections, and other acquired neurological disorders (Slowik et al., 2024).

Response to Treatment: Improvement or resolution of symptoms upon cessation of toxin exposure supports the diagnosis of toxin-induced CSA (Cumpston & Chen, 2023).

Table 3 provides an overview of the various diagnostic aspects and management considerations for toxin-induced CSA.

Table 3. Toxin-Induced CSA Diagnostic Aspects and Management Considerations

Aspect	Description
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Patient History	Detailed exposure history documenting duration, intensity, and type of organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals (Institute of Medicine, 1995)
Physical Examination	Focus on respiratory symptoms during sleep; assess for neurological signs indicating CNS involvement (Slowik et al., 2024)
Neuroimaging	MRI detects brain structural abnormalities or toxicity signs in CSA-related brain regions (Ciumas et al., 2022; Yuan et al., 2022)
Laboratory Tests	Blood and urine tests measure toxin levels (e.g., lead, organic solvents); elevated levels suggest CSA-related exposure (Wani et al., 2016)
Biomarkers	Assess biomarkers indicating neurotoxic damage or metabolic disturbances from toxin exposure (Roberts et al., 2015)
Neurological Examination	Assess sensory abnormalities, reflexes (including respiratory), and balance for broader neurological assessment related to CSA (Shahrokhi & Asuncion, 2023)
Polysomnographic Testing	Sleep study (polysomnography) monitors physiological parameters to differentiate CSA from OSA (Akbarian et al., 2020; Gerstenslager & Slowik, 2023)
Neurophysiological Testing	ABR evaluates brainstem function crucial for breathing regulation, assessing neural involvement in CSA (Young et al., 2023)
Exclusion of Other Causes	Differential diagnosis excludes inherited disorders, autoimmune conditions, infections, and other neurological disorders (Slowik et al., 2024)
Response to Treatment	Improvement upon toxin exposure cessation supports diagnosis of toxin-induced CSA (Cumpston & Chen, 2023)

This detailed approach provides specific criteria and diagnostic considerations for identifying CSA caused by environmental toxin exposure, facilitating accurate diagnosis and appropriate management strategies.

CSA: Neuropathophysiological Pathways (Considerations for Differential Diagnosis or Contributing Factors)

Inherited Causes of CSA

Inherited CSA is a less common subset often associated with genetic mutations affecting various CNS components. These conditions can present with persistent sleep-related breathing issues and may be classified based on the pattern of inheritance and the specific genetic mutation involved (Dempsey, 2019).

Inherited causes of CSA include:

- **Genetic mutations:** Mutations in specific genes (e.g., PHOX2B) have been associated with congenital central hypoventilation syndrome (CCHS), a condition leading to CSA (Bishara, Keens, & Perez, 2018)
- **Familial CSA:** Some forms of CSA occur within families, suggesting a hereditary component, although specific genetic mutations may not always be identified (Mukherjee, Saxena, & Palmer, 2018)
- **Neurodegenerative disorders:** Certain genetic conditions that lead to neurodegeneration (e.g., multiple system atrophy) can also cause CSA (Anghel et al., 2023)
- **Formation of dental supporting structures and teeth (Annexure 3)**

Identification and testing:

- **Patient history and physical examination:** Comprehensive evaluation to elucidate characteristic features (e.g., onset, pattern of progression, distribution of symptoms, and associated systemic manifestations)
- **Polysomnography:** Sleep studies to assess breathing patterns, apneas, and hypopneas, detecting potential CNS dysfunction during sleep (Gerstenslager & Slowik, 2023)

- **Genetic testing:** Confirmatory diagnosis through identification of specific mutations

Advancements in genetic sequencing technologies facilitate targeted testing for known mutations and expand understanding of genotype-phenotype correlations (Mukherjee et al., 2018).

Acquired Causes of CSA

Acquired CSA results from various external factors that disrupt normal respiratory function, particularly within the CNS (Rana & Sankari, 2023).

Acquired causes of CSA include:

- **Alcoholism:** Chronic alcohol abuse leads to neurotoxicity and disruption of central respiratory control
- **Autoimmune diseases:** Conditions, e.g., systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) and multiple sclerosis, leading to inflammation and immune attacks on the CNS
- **Cancers and paraneoplastic syndromes:** Immune-mediated mechanisms or direct CNS invasion leading to CSA
- **Chemotherapy:** Neurotoxic effects of agents (e.g., cisplatin) affecting central respiratory control
- **Chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy (CIDP):** Autoimmune disorder affecting both peripheral and CNSs, impacting respiratory pathways
- **Chronic kidney disease:** Uremia leading to CNS dysfunction and CSA
- **Diabetes mellitus:** Vascular damage and metabolic disturbances in the CNS due to prolonged hyperglycemia
- **Hypothyroidism:** Metabolic changes and CNS dysfunction contributing to CSA
- **Infections:** Encephalitis, HIV/AIDS, neurotropic viruses leading to damage in central respiratory control pathways
- **Injury to dental supporting structures and teeth (Annexure 3)**
- **Trauma and nerve compression:** Physical injuries to the CNS
- **Vitamin deficiencies:** Deficiencies in B1 (thiamine), B6 (pyridoxine), and B12 (cobalamin) affect CNS function
- **Exposure to toxins:** Organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals lead to neurotoxicity and CNS dysfunction (National Research Council, 1990)

CSA: Diagnostic Approach and Progression

Clinical Evaluation

Diagnosing CSA begins with a thorough medical history and physical examination. The clinical evaluation focuses on identifying the characteristics of sleep-related breathing issues, assessing potential triggers, and considering associated symptoms. A detailed history of possible exposures (e.g., toxins and trauma), family history of respiratory or neurological disorders, and systemic diseases can provide critical clues (Cumpston & Chen, 2023).

Laboratory Investigations

Laboratory tests: Laboratory tests can help identify underlying causes of CSA (e.g., metabolic disorders, infections, or autoimmune conditions). Blood tests may assess levels of electrolytes, glucose, thyroid function, and specific antibodies. Imaging studies, i.e., MRI or computed tomography (CT) scans, can evaluate structural abnormalities in the brain, particularly in the respiratory control centers (van Beek & Hoffman, 2008).

Screening for exposure to neurotoxic substances: Screening involves laboratory tests to detect toxins, including markers and metabolites of organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals (National Research Council, 1992). Blood and urine tests can measure levels of specific toxins or their metabolites, helping to identify environmental or occupational exposures contributing to CSA (Mukherji, Azhar, & Sharma, 2023).

Polysomnographic Testing

Polysomnography is a comprehensive sleep study that monitors various physiological parameters during sleep, including brain waves, oxygen levels in the blood, heart rate, breathing patterns, and eye and leg movements (Gerstenslager & Slowik, 2023). The data collected helps to differentiate between OSA and CSA by identifying central apneas where there is a lack of respiratory effort (Akbarian et al., 2020).

Neurophysiological Testing

Although primarily used for auditory conditions, ABR testing can be adapted to evaluate the brainstem's function, which is crucial in regulating breathing. This test can provide metrics about the nature and extent of neural involvement in CSA (Young et al., 2023).

Genetic Testing

Genetic testing can identify inherited disorders associated with CSA. Identifying specific genetic mutations can provide a definitive diagnosis and guide treatment strategies (Mukherjee et al., 2018). Genetic testing may be useful for syndromic forms of CSA associated with other hereditary conditions (Mukherjee et al., 2018).

Table 4 summarizes the primary and secondary symptoms of CSA and how these symptoms can affect both sleep and waking states.

Table 4. CSA Symptoms and Their Impact

CSA Symptoms	Description
Primary Symptoms (During Sleep)	Repeated pauses in breathing due to brain's intermittent failure to signal respiratory muscles
Secondary Symptoms (During Waking State)	
Daytime Fatigue	Excessive daytime sleepiness and fatigue due to poor sleep quality
Difficulty Concentrating	Cognitive issues (e.g., trouble focusing, memory problems, and impaired judgment) caused by interrupted sleep
Morning Headaches	Headaches upon waking, often due to reduced oxygen levels during sleep
Mood Changes	Irritability, anxiety, and depression resulting from sleep disturbances
Shortness of Breath	Sensation of breathlessness during the day, especially in individuals with concurrent heart or lung conditions

Sources: Cumpston & Chen, 2023; Rana & Sankari, 2023; Shah & Pandey, 2019

CSA: Treatment and Management Related to Environmental Toxin Exposure

Identifying and Eliminating the Source

Managing CSA begins with identifying and eliminating exposure to environmental toxins that may contribute to respiratory symptoms. This process involves comprehensively evaluating occupational history, environmental exposures, and lifestyle factors that could impact respiratory health (Dempsey, 2019). When indicated, collaboration among pulmonologists, cardiologists, neurologists, sleep medicine specialists (Haq et al., 2021), psychologists, psychiatrists, radiologists, dentists (Trăistaru, Pantea, Maria Cristina Țâncu, & Imre, 2022), toxicologists (National Research Council, 1992), and internists* is essential to formulate an effective management plan (Fleetham et al., 2011).

* Internists might be involved in the diagnosis and management of CSA when it is related to systemic conditions and may coordinate care with specialists such as cardiologists or pulmonologists (Fleetham et al., 2011).

Pharmacological Interventions

Pharmacological treatment of CSA aims to alleviate symptoms and improve quality of life (QoL). While no medication explicitly cures CSA, particular drugs may help manage symptoms and underlying mechanisms:

- **Respiratory stimulants:** Medications, e.g., acetazolamide and theophylline can stimulate breathing and reduce the frequency of central apneas (Rana & Sankari, 2023).
- **Antioxidants:** Supplements, e.g., alpha-lipoic acid and N-acetylcysteine, may reduce oxidative stress associated with toxin-induced damage (Rodella, Honisch, Gatto, Ruzza, & D'Amato Tóthová, 2023).
- **Neuroprotective agents:** Medications, e.g., memantine or piracetam, are under investigation for their potential to protect neurons from toxin-induced injury (Chayrov et al., 2022).
- **Anxiolytics:** Drugs, e.g., benzodiazepines, may help alleviate associated anxiety and distress caused by persistent CSA (World Health Organization, 2009).

Adjunctive Therapies

Therapeutic interventions play a crucial role in managing CSA and improving overall respiratory function:

- **Positive airway pressure (PAP) therapy:** Continuous PAP (CPAP) or adaptive servo-ventilation (ASV) devices help maintain airway patency and reduce apneas during sleep (Pinto & Sharma, 2023).
- **Oxygen therapy:** Supplemental oxygen can help maintain adequate oxygen levels during sleep, particularly in cases with significant hypoxemia (Weekley & Bland, 2023).
- **Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT):** Psychological interventions can help patients manage anxiety and improve coping mechanisms related to CSA (Altena, Ellis, Camart, Guichard, & Bastien, 2023).

Nutritional Support

Addressing nutritional deficiencies is integral to supporting respiratory health and managing toxin-induced CSA:

- **Vitamin supplements:** Adequate intake of vitamins (e.g., B12, B6, and folate) may mitigate neurotoxic effects and support nerve function (Baltrusch, 2021).

- **Mineral supplementation:** Magnesium and zinc supplements have been studied for their potential role in reducing CSA severity (Hamedifard et al., 2020).

Monitoring and Regular Follow-Up

Regular monitoring is essential to assess treatment efficacy and adjust management strategies as needed. Polysomnographic evaluations, subjective sleep quality assessments, and medical imaging are used to guide therapeutic interventions, assess their efficacy, and monitor changes in symptoms over time (Fabbri et al., 2021).

Education and Counseling

Patient education and counseling are pivotal in managing CSA associated with environmental toxins:

- **Education:** Providing information about CSA, its potential causes, and management strategies promote active patient participation in care (Institute of Medicine, 2006b; Kerna et al., 2024).
- **Counseling:** Addressing the emotional and psychological impact of chronic CSA through counseling can improve coping skills and QoL (Kerna et al., 2024; Rana & Sankari, 2023).

This comprehensive approach to managing toxin-induced CSA underscores the importance of early detection, targeted interventions, and ongoing support to optimize patient outcomes and mitigate the impact on respiratory health.

CSA: Sleep Stage Specificity

CSA primarily occurs during the non-rapid eye movement (NREM) sleep stages. Specifically, it is most common during the lighter stages of NREM sleep (N1 and N2), though it can also occur in the deeper NREM stages (N3; Edwards et al., 2010).

CSA is less common during rapid eye movement (REM) sleep. During REM sleep, the body's control of breathing becomes more irregular due to the brain's increased activity and muscle relaxation. However, OSA is more likely to occur during this stage than CSA (Edwards et al., 2010).

Conclusion

Organic solvents, pesticides, and heavy metals exert neurotoxic effects, contributing to various medical conditions, including central sleep apnea (CSA). These toxins disrupt neural function through several mechanisms, each exacerbating the risk of CSA development. Organic solvents, prevalent in industrial and household products, penetrate the body via inhalation, ingestion, or skin contact. They disrupt neuronal membranes by altering lipid bilayers, compromising membrane integrity crucial for neuronal signaling. This disruption impairs the release of neurotransmitters and synaptic transmission, both of which are crucial for regulating breathing during sleep. Imbalances in neurotransmitters, e.g., gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) and glutamate, further disturb neural excitability, exacerbating CSA symptoms by hindering the brain's ability to maintain respiratory rhythms. Pesticides, widely used in agriculture, penetrate the body via inhalation, ingestion, or skin contact. They inhibit enzymes involved in neurotransmitter metabolism, which leads to excessive accumulation of neurotransmitters and disruption of signaling pathways. Also, they interfere directly with neurotransmitter receptors, impairing normal nerve signal transmission in the brainstem. Oxidative stress caused by pesticides exacerbates these effects by damaging neurons and compromising mitochondrial function. This cascade of events diminishes the brain's capacity to regulate breathing patterns, culminating in apnea episodes during sleep. Heavy metals, prevalent in industrial pollutants and e-waste, enter the body via inhalation and ingestion or penetrate via skin contact. They disrupt neuronal ion channels and induce oxidative stress and inflammatory responses. These metals impair ion channel function (crucial for generating nerve impulses)

and trigger oxidative damage to cellular components, including mitochondria. Such disruptions in the brainstem's respiratory control centers impair its ability to sustain normal breathing rhythms, contributing significantly to CSA development. Diagnosing toxin-induced CSA involves detailed patient history, physical examination, neuroimaging, and laboratory tests to identify exposure levels and associated neurological damage. Treatment and management strategies include eliminating toxin exposure, pharmacological interventions to mitigate symptoms, and adjunctive therapies like positive airway pressure (PAP) devices and cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). Effective management of toxin-induced CSA requires a multidisciplinary approach, integrating pulmonology, neurology, and toxicology to optimize patient outcomes and quality of life (QoL).

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that this paper was written without any commercial or financial relationship that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Annexures

Annexure 1. Association of Central Sleep Apnea (CSA) and Women’s Health

CSA has significant implications for various aspects of women’s health, including pregnancy and fertility. CSA can have detrimental effects on physiological and hormonal balance, which are vital for reproductive health.

Table A1 summarizes the impact of CSA on pregnancy and fertility.

Table A1. Impact of CSA on Pregnancy and Fertility

Aspect	Impact
Impact on Pregnancy	Fetal Outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intermittent hypoxia from CSA can reduce oxygen delivery, leading to intrauterine growth restriction, preterm birth, and low birth weight • Increased risk of preeclampsia and gestational hypertension
	Maternal Complications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher risk of hypertension, heart failure, and exacerbation of cardiovascular conditions • Can lead to poor maternal and fetal outcomes
Impact on Fertility	Hormonal Disruption <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSA can affect fertility through hormonal imbalances by disrupting the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis • May cause irregular menstrual cycles, reduced ovarian function, and difficulties conceiving
	Treatment Considerations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) therapy may improve sleep quality and mitigate risks • Use during pregnancy should be monitored to ensure safety for both mother and fetus

CSA has notable effects on women’s reproductive health, influencing both pregnancy outcomes and fertility. Effective management of CSA is crucial to mitigate these effects and promote overall health and well-being (Bin, Cistulli, & Ford, 2016; Kember, Elangainesan, Ferraro, Jones, & Hobson, 2023; Li, Zhao, Hua, & Li, 2018).

Annexure 2. Lead Pipes and Drinking Water

Lead pipes in drinking water systems pose significant hazards to individuals, particularly to vulnerable populations such as children and pregnant women. Exposure to lead through drinking water can result in severe health consequences. In children, it can lead to developmental delays, learning difficulties, irritability, weight loss, fatigue, and hearing loss. The most concerning effects are neurological, as lead poisoning can cause cognitive impairments and behavioral issues, ultimately lowering intelligence quotient (IQ) and hindering academic performance. Adults are not spared; they face risks of high blood pressure, cardiovascular disease, kidney damage, and reproductive health issues, including complications during pregnancy (Olufemi, Mji, & Mukhola, 2022).

Table A2 summarizes the effects of lead exposure from lead pipe drinking water in children and adults.

Table A2: Effects of Lead Exposure from Lead Pipe Drinking Water

Effects in Children
Developmental delays
Learning difficulties
Irritability
Weight loss
Fatigue

Hearing loss
Neurological effects (cognitive impairments, lowered IQ, behavioral issues)
Effects in Adults
High blood pressure
Cardiovascular disease
Kidney damage
Reproductive health issues, including pregnancy complications

The current public discourse and debate surrounding lead pipes and drinking water are highly charged—fueled by incidents like the Flint, Michigan, USA water crisis. Public concern is widespread, with communities demanding safer drinking water and stricter regulatory standards. There is significant debate over the adequacy of existing regulations and whether they effectively protect public health. Funding is another contentious issue, with arguments over whether federal, state, or local governments or even homeowners should shoulder the financial burden of replacing lead pipes. Additionally, there is a growing focus on health equity, as marginalized and low-income communities often suffer the most from lead contamination (Jacobson, Boufides, Bernstein, Chrysler, & Citrin, 2018; Pauli, 2020).

In response to these challenges, various public health initiatives have been launched. Educational campaigns aim to raise awareness about the dangers of lead exposure and ways to minimize risk. Programs for testing water in homes, schools, and public buildings help identify and mitigate exposure. Health screenings for children, especially in high-risk areas, are crucial for early detection and intervention. These initiatives are vital for protecting public health and preventing long-term health consequences (Ruckart et al., 2019).

Public health and government programs play a pivotal role in addressing this issue. The USA Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has implemented the Lead and Copper Rule to control lead levels in drinking water, and recent revisions aim to enhance detection and removal efforts. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) provides guidelines and resources for lead poisoning prevention, supporting local health departments (Jacobson et al., 2018). The USA Department of Housing and Urban Development (HUD) coordinates programs to eliminate lead-based paint hazards that address lead in water (Breyse, Cascio, Geller, Choiniere, & Ammon, 2022).

Government initiatives are critical in resolving the lead pipe drinking water issue. The USA Bipartisan Infrastructure Law (first proposed in 2021 and officially known as the Infrastructure Investment and Jobs Act) has allocated billions of dollars to replace lead pipes and service lines nationwide. State and local governments can access various grants and funding programs to support these efforts. Many cities have established lead service line replacement programs, prioritizing high-risk areas to ensure the most vulnerable populations are protected first. Regulatory enhancements aim to limit allowable lead levels in drinking water, increasing monitoring and compliance requirements. Public-private partnerships also play a role in accelerating the removal and replacement of lead pipes, leveraging resources and expertise from both sectors (DeFazio, 2021; Jain, Bajaj, & Stanford, 2022).

Annexure 3. Association Between Central Sleep Apnea (CSA) and Dental Conditions

There is a potential association between CSA and certain dental conditions, primarily through their impact on the upper airway and respiratory function.

1. **Structural Issues:** Dental and craniofacial structures can influence upper airway anatomy. Conditions, such as retrognathia (receding chin), micrognathia (small jaw), or enlarged tonsils can contribute to airway obstruction during sleep, potentially exacerbating CSA.

2. **Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA) Overlap:** OSA, which involves repetitive partial or complete obstruction of the upper airway during sleep, can sometimes coexist with CSA. Dental conditions such as dental malocclusions (misalignment of teeth and jaws) can contribute to OSA, which may influence or worsen CSA.

3. **Oral Appliances:** Dental professionals can play a role in managing sleep-related breathing disorders through oral appliances. Mandibular advancement devices (MADs) are designed to reposition the lower jaw and tongue to maintain airway patency during sleep, potentially benefiting patients with CSA or OSA.

4. **Treatment Coordination:** Collaborative care between dentists and sleep medicine specialists is essential for diagnosing and managing sleep apnea disorders. Dental evaluations focusing on airway anatomy and oral health can complement medical assessments, ensuring comprehensive treatment planning.

While CSA primarily involves neurological and respiratory factors, dental conditions and treatments can influence airway dynamics and potentially impact sleep-related breathing disorders (Chang et al., 2023; Cielo, Montalva, & Taylor, 2016).